

Transcending Barriers

Project number 101144262

METHODOLOGY GUIDE

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**Promoting Trans Inclusion
in the Workplace**

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Introduction

This document outlines the methodological guidelines for implementing research conducted as part of the *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace* (TB) project. The methodological guide provides an overview of the approach to the research, data collection techniques, ethical considerations, data management protocols and sample documents to carry out the project. The aim of the document is to assist partners with both the fieldwork and the data analysis and to conduct the research in a standardized way that facilitates comparisons. As a living document, it will be continuously updated throughout the duration of the project to refine the details of its implementation. In the event of significant changes, the ethics committee will be informed.

The project will follow the established ethical considerations and the ethical obligations applicable in each country where the research is being conducted, including securing clearance from ethics committees when applicable. In addition, each partner will adhere to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The TB project was designed to promote trans inclusion in the workplace by enhancing the skills of human resources professionals, raising awareness and supporting trans individuals through mentoring programmes. The methodology guide for the associated research provides the basis for achieving these goals. The project, which operates in a number of European countries, aligns with the European Union's equality strategies and relevant legislative frameworks. In short, it aims to support the implementation of EU policies to combat workplace discrimination and promote inclusivity.

Guiding themes

The guiding themes (GT) are the fundamental areas of interest that structure the processes of data collection and analysis in most of the tasks related to the TB project. These indicators are dynamic and flexible, reflecting the project's inherently reflective nature. This means that, on the one hand, they evolve in response to the evolution of the research and activities, allowing for the inclusion, removal or modification of any indicator. At the same time, they enable adaptation based on contextual factors and the ongoing progress of the project.

The GTs guide the methodological processes, fieldwork and data analysis so that findings can be compared across scientific disciplines, rather than establishing fixed and immutable categories. The GTs listed below provide the foundation for the questions and discussion topics that appear in the interviews and surveys.

GT1. The dichotomy of gender as a social, cultural and historical construct

Gender is structured within a heteropatriarchal social order, which both materializes and symbolically constructs social organization by using the heterosexual male model as its reference point.¹ This order establishes power relations and inequalities that shape perceptions of women and other gender identities or expressions. Those who do not conform to the hegemonic ideal are rendered invisible and stigmatized.² As a result, individuals are compelled to conform to a pre-established, hierarchical binary gender model. The binary gender system is neither neutral nor universal; it is a product of historically and culturally embedded norms rooted in Western epistemologies and reinforced through colonial systems of domination.

The gender binary obscures sexual diversity – denying intersexuality – and enforces the notion of two distinct, mutually exclusive, dichotomous, complementary and hierarchically ordered genders.³

This project uses ‘trans’ as an umbrella term, embracing its openness and non-specificity, which allows for the inclusion of a wide range of gender identities and experiences.⁴ This understanding of the term encompasses both binary trans individuals (those who transition from one binary gender to the other binary gender) and non-binary people (such as genderqueer or genderfluid). However, in this document, the term ‘trans and non-binary people/individuals’ is used to explicitly include participants who, while non-binary, may not fully identify with the trans umbrella.

GT2. Work as access to material assets, resources and services

For the trans community, employment is not merely an economic opportunity, but a fundamental pillar of full social integration, well-being and recognition of trans individuals as inherently valuable, interdependent human beings. In this respect, Judith Butler’s book, *The Force of Nonviolence: An Ethico-Political Bind*⁵ delves into how violence manifests through the regulation of the ‘grievability of lives’, demonstrating how this regulation is deeply intertwined with concepts of individualism, interdependence and equality. Butler argues that when certain lives are not

¹ Dyer, Hannah. 2016. ‘Queer Futurity and Childhood Innocence: Beyond the Injury of Development’, *Global Studies of Childhood* 7 (3): 290-302. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043610616671056>.

² Butler, Judith. 2004. *Undoing Gender*. New York: Routledge.

³ Platero, Lucas. 2014. *Trans*Exualidades: Acompañamiento, Factores de Salud Y Recursos Educativos*. Barcelona: Bellaterra.

⁴ Halberstam, Jack. 2018. *Trans: A Quick and Quirky Account of Gender Variability*. Oakland, California: University Of California Press. & Tompkins, Avery, *TSQ. Transgender Studies Quarterly*, 1: (1-2): 26-27.

⁵ Butler, Judith. 2020. *The Force of Nonviolence: An Ethico-Political Bind*. London, New York: Verso.

recognized as grievable, they are less likely to be protected and valued. From this perspective, the exclusion of trans people from the labour market – thereby denying them access to material resources, services and economic stability – constitutes a form of structural violence that reinforces their marginalization and vulnerability.

In a critique that is particularly relevant to the question of employment, Butler challenges the dominance of individualism in ethical and political thought, emphasizing instead the concept of intrinsic interdependence. Lives are fundamentally interconnected, and access to work should not be seen as a purely individual matter, but as a critical factor in enabling a liveable and equitable existence. The denial of employment opportunities to trans individuals not only deprives them of essential material resources, but also weakens social bonds and perpetuates systemic inequality.

Equality, in this sense, does not merely concern abstract concepts of equal treatment, but requires a reorganization of society to ensure fair access to material necessities such as food, housing, work and infrastructure. In this context, the inclusion of trans people in the workspace is a vital issue of social justice, directly linked to their recognition as valued and grievable lives.

GT3. Intersectionality

Intersectionality refers to the various structural sources of inequality that interact with one another, highlighting the fact that categories such as gender, ethnicity, class and sexual orientation are socially constructed and inherently interconnected.⁶ The intersectional perspective challenges the idea that individual experiences can be understood as a mere sum of different forms of inequality or exclusion. Rather, these relational categories are embodied, fluid and deeply intertwined, making them analytically inseparable.⁷ Factors from gender to trans visibility, age, race, cultural background, disability to body size and societal beauty standards directly shape the lived experiences of trans individuals.

Focusing solely on trans identity as a singular dimension of inequality risks overlooking individuals affected by the intersection of multiple forms of marginalization. Thus, it is crucial to consider how different axes of inequality interact. Rather than compiling an exhaustive list of inequalities, the approach used here identifies the most relevant identities in each context, examining how people embody them to create meaning. This involves not only understanding the

⁶ Salem, Sara. 2014. 'Feminismo Islámico, Interseccionalidad y Decolonialidad', *Tabula Rasa*, no. 21 (December): 111–22. <https://doi.org/10.25058/20112742.6>.

⁷ Platero, Lucas. 2012. '¿Son Las Políticas de Igualdad de Género Permeables a Los Debates Sobre La Interseccionalidad? Una Reflexión a Partir Del Caso Español', *Revista Del CLAD Reforma y Democracia*, no. 52: 135-72. <http://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=357533684005..>

impact of discrimination, but also interrogating the categories on which it is based. The analysis here explores the mutual relationships between these categories, paying particular attention to how they contribute to structural exclusion while simultaneously fostering unique strategies of resistance and empowerment.⁸

In a broader context, this study also provides an opportunity to examine the experiences of individuals without work visas or labour permits, who often access employment through the informal economy. Additionally, it considers those who, despite being legally eligible to work, opt to remain outside the formal labour system, for instance people engaged in sex work. Addressing these realities is an essential part of fully understanding the intersections between labour, legal status and systemic inequality.

GT4. Discrimination and violence: psychosocial and physical impact

According to the minority stress model,⁹ an excess of social stressors related to stigma, prejudice and discrimination leads to a higher prevalence of mental health issues for LGBTIQ+ people when compared to heterosexual individuals. Scholars in the field argue that violence against LGBTIQ+ individuals is embedded within the broader structure of a cisheteropatriarchal society, where heterosexism operates as an ideological system that denies, denigrates and stigmatizes non-heterosexual behaviours, identities, relationships and communities.^{10, 11}

Findings suggest that sexual minorities experience stigma at multiple levels – individual, interpersonal, structural¹² – impacting both their mental and physical health,¹³ and that sexual

⁸ Salem, Sara. 2014. 'Feminismo Islámico, Interseccionalidad y Decolonialidad', *Tabula Rasa*, no. 21 (December): 111-22. <https://doi.org/10.25058/20112742.6>.

⁹ Meyer, Ilan H. 2003. 'Prejudice, Social Stress, and Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Populations: Conceptual Issues and Research Evidence', *Psychological Bulletin* 129 (5): 674-97. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.5.674>.

¹⁰ Bell, James G., and Barbara Perry. 2014. 'Outside Looking In: The Community Impacts of Anti-Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Hate Crime', *Journal of Homosexuality* 62 (1): 98-120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2014.957133>.

¹¹ Herek, Gregory M. 1992. 'The social context of hate crimes: Notes on cultural heterosexism', in *Hate Crimes: Confronting Violence against Lesbians and Gay Men*, ed. Gregory Herek & Kevin Berrill (Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 1992), 89-104.

¹² White Hughto, Jaclyn M., Sari L. Reisner, and John E. Pachankis. 2015. 'Transgender Stigma and Health: A Critical Review of Stigma Determinants, Mechanisms, and Interventions', *Social Science & Medicine* 147 (December): 222-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2015.11.010>.

¹³ Lick, David J., Laura E. Durso, and Kerri L. Johnson. 2013. 'Minority Stress and Physical Health among Sexual Minorities', *Perspectives on Psychological Science* 8 (5): 521-48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691613497965>.

minorities experience disproportionately high rates of mental health issues.^{14, 15} A recent systematic review¹⁶ found a higher prevalence of mental health disorders among trans individuals, with studies suggesting that the risk of receiving a psychiatric diagnosis is twice as high for transgender individuals than their cisgender peers,¹⁷ with ratios that range from 1.5:1 for being diagnosed with a mood disorder, 3.9:1 for an anxiety disorder and 3.8:1 for a psychotic disorder. Moreover, the prevalence of non-suicidal self-injurious behaviours and completed suicide has been estimated to be 13 times higher in the trans population. The prevalence of these results appears consistent throughout different geographical areas.¹⁸

GT5. Resilience/resistance as a strategy against violence

Resilience has traditionally been defined as an individual's capacity to respond to adverse situations. The initial dominant psychological paradigm limited the conceptualization of resilience to an individual trait or personal capacity to cope, recover and adapt through negative experiences and stress.¹⁹ However, more recent research has expanded to examine resilience at the macro- and meso-levels, incorporating a socioecological framework. This framework highlights the ways in which societal structures, institutions and protective factors – like social support and resources – shape resilience.^{20, 21} This shift emphasizes the idea that resilience is not an inherent trait, but rather a dynamic, context-specific social process that is deeply influenced by social, political and economic factors, affecting how individuals interact with their

¹⁴ David M. Fergusson, L. John Horwood, Elizabeth M. Ridder, and Annette L. Beautrais, 'Sexual Orientation and Mental Health in a Birth Cohort of Young Adults', *Psychological Medicine* 35, no. 7 (2005): 971-81, <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291704004222>.

¹⁵ Sandfort, Theo G.M., Floor Bakker, François G. Schellevis, and Ine Vanwesenbeeck. 2006. 'Sexual Orientation and Mental and Physical Health Status: Findings from a Dutch Population Survey', *American Journal of Public Health* 96 (6): 1119-25. <https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.2004.058891>.

¹⁶ Pinna, Federica, Pasquale Paribello, Giulia Somaini, Alice Corona, Antonio Ventriglio, Carolina Corrias, Ilaria Frau, et al. 2022. 'Mental Health in Transgender Individuals: A Systematic Review', *International Review of Psychiatry* 34 (3-4): 292-359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540261.2022.2093629>.

¹⁷ Hanna, Bishoy, Rupak Desai, Tarang Parekh, Erenie Guirguis, Gautam Kumar, and Rajesh Sachdeva. 2019. 'Psychiatric Disorders in the U.S. Transgender Population', *Annals of Epidemiology* 39 (November): 1-7.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annepidem.2019.09.009>.

¹⁸ García-Vega, Elena, Aida Camero, María Fernández, and Ana Villaverde. 2018. 'Suicidal Ideation and Suicide Attempts in Persons with Gender Dysphoria', *Psicothema* 30 (3): 283-88. <https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2017.438>.

¹⁹ Qamar, Azher Hameed. 2024. 'Social Resilience: A Critical Synopsis of Definitions', *Corvinus Journal of Sociology and Social Policy* 15 (1): 129-47. <https://doi.org/10.14267/cjssp.2024.1.6>.

²⁰ Asakura, Kenta. 2016. 'Paving Pathways through the Pain: A Grounded Theory of Resilience among Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, and Queer Youth', *Journal of Research on Adolescence* 27 (3): 521-36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12291>.

²¹ Ungar, Michael. 2011. 'The Social Ecology of Resilience: Addressing Contextual and Cultural Ambiguity of a Nascent Construct', *The American Journal of Orthopsychiatry* 81 (1): 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1939-0025.2010.01067.x>.

environments.²² Studies of gender and sexual violence often focus on the mechanisms and relationships of violence and discrimination, frequently overlooking the strategies developed by those affected to navigate and resist these situations. This approach often portrays women and LGBTIQ+ individuals as passive victims, primarily defined by the impact of gender violence and LGBTIQ+-phobia and neglecting their agency.

By contrast, this project considers trans participants as active agents capable of developing both individual and collective mechanisms of resilience. It recognizes the central role that LGBTIQ+ activism has played in shaping these forms of resistance, advancing rights and lobbying for the legal and social recognition of gender and sexual diversity. Through advocacy, visibility and community organizing, LGBTIQ+ movements have not only demanded protections, but have also built networks of care, support and self-determination that continue to challenge structural violence and exclusion.

GT6. Legal protection and workplace policies

Although not sufficient on their own, legal protections and inclusive workplace policies are essential tools for addressing discrimination against trans individuals. They provide a necessary framework for institutional accountability and signal a commitment to trans rights. When paired with effective implementation – such as training and monitoring – they contribute to building safer, more supportive work environments and challenging structural inequalities.

There are important legislative differences between the countries participating in the study, particularly the lack of specific protections for trans rights in Bulgaria. Italy, Spain and Lithuania have taken some steps to address workplace discrimination, although significant gaps remain. In Italy, for instance, a 2019 report²³ indicated that only 16 per cent of trans individuals had stable employment, while 62 per cent of those seeking work were unemployed. In Spain, national and regional studies have shown that trans individuals experience higher unemployment rates than the general population, in addition to recurring workplace discrimination.²⁴ In Lithuania, qualitative research has observed that employment-related discrimination remains one of the main challenges for trans individuals.²⁵ By contrast, Bulgaria

²² Robinson, Brandon Andrew, and Rachel M. Schmitz. 2021. 'Beyond Resilience: Resistance in the Lives of LGBTQ Youth', *Sociology Compass* 15 (12). <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.12947>.

²³ Movimento Identità Trans (MIT), <https://mit-italia.it/>

²⁴ Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE), *Report*, 2019; Fundación Triángulo, *Informe sobre el empleo trans en España (Report on Trans Employment in Spain)* (Madrid: Fundación Triángulo, 2018).

²⁵LGL. 2016. *TRANS_LT: Documenting Experiences of Transgender People in Employment*. Vilnius: Lithuanian Gay League.

lacks specific legal recognition of trans identities, and no national data is available apart from broader European reports. This absence of legal frameworks and institutional support hinders trans individuals' access to safe and equitable employment.

Objectives, risks and contingency measures

Project objectives

This project aims to achieve the following general objectives in the medium- to long-term:

1. Promoting LGBTIQ+ inclusion in employment by strengthening the abilities of HR professionals and managers to engage in diversity management practices with special reference to trans individuals
2. Preparing and developing a training curriculum to address the training needs of HR professionals and managers in the field of LGBTIQ+ diversity management
3. Enhancing knowledge about and the application of trans people's equal rights in the workplace in the countries involved through awareness-raising activities
4. Improving access to the workplace through mentoring activities that target trans individuals

Analytical activities

The project will begin with a set of analytical activities aimed at ensuring that all subsequent actions are grounded in evidence and to effectively respond to the real needs of the target groups.

This phase will focus on four core objectives:

1) Analysing training needs (using the following methods)

- Survey on the needs of target groups (TG) and indirect beneficiaries (IB) (quantitative research): a minimum 400 participants
 - Survey 1: Needs of HR professionals and managers
 - Survey 2: Trans + IB needs
- Interviews with key actors related to TG and IB needs (qualitative research): a minimum of 40 semi-structured interviews (roughly 10 for each country involved) to gather in-depth information about TG and IB needs.

The analysis of training needs is a critical stage of the project, because it ensures that the subsequent activities are based on reliable training needs assessments, rather than assumptions. At the same time, the primary function of the analytical activities in the project is to inform the subsequent actions, ensuring maximum practical benefits and impact for the target groups.

2) Designing the training curriculum

On the basis of the information about the training needs gathered, a training curriculum will be designed to build capacity in the area of trans inclusion and diversity management, targeting HR professionals and managers. Parts of the curriculum will be identical in all the countries to ensure conceptual clarity and a consistent approach, but there will also be some room for country-specific portions (the partners will customize legislation, best practices, etc.).

3) Mentoring guidelines

The data collected through the qualitative and quantitative methods (together with desk research) will be used as a baseline to produce the mentoring guidelines in a practical handbook for mentors to use with trans and non-binary mentees.

By relying on rigorous participatory research methods, this phase will lay the groundwork for the entire project, ensuring that all outputs are context-sensitive, relevant and capable of having a long-term, sustainable impact. To achieve the objectives in this analytical phase, the following tasks will be carried out:

- Producing the methodology guide
- Creating the standardized interview and survey model
- Conducting semi-structured in-depth interviews (all partners/every country)
- Conducting online surveys (all partners/every country)
- Analysing training needs (all partners/every country)
- Desk research
- Creating a training curriculum

Risks and contingency measures

Risks	Contingency measures
Delays in project implementation Probability: medium Impact: medium	The project team has carefully studied the various aspects of the project to avoid unforeseen delays. The project's management plan will also be designed to handle unforeseen events that could cause delays.
Staff turnover Probability: medium Impact: low	Core staff are permanent staff or recruited experts who have a long-term professional interest in addressing LGBTIQ+ issues and therefore have a strong commitment to work until the end of the project. If core staff members need to be replaced, partners will ensure that someone with similar experience is recruited to take their place.

<p>Defaulting partner Probability: very low Impact: medium/high</p>	<p>The responsibilities of the partners will be clearly stated in the consortium agreement. The steering committee will then determine how these obligations will be handled.</p>
<p>Time-consuming data collection Probability: low Impact: medium</p>	<p>The project timeline allocates several months to the task, which should allow for a proper search through national and international databases and the academic literature, as well as conducting data collection. If this is not enough, efforts will be made to ensure that the entire research team joins forces and works together, maximizing the efforts.</p>
<p>Rapid changes in in-country legal frameworks Probability: low Impact: low</p>	<p>The progression towards full LGBTIQ+ equality has been slow in recent years and rapid changes are unlikely to take place during the lifecycle of the project. However, if necessary, the time dedicated to the needs assessment will be extended, making it possible to integrate any new data.</p>
<p>Training curriculum does not respond to training needs Probability: low Impact: high</p>	<p>The training curriculum will be structured following the analysis of the training needs, ensuring that it will address real gaps and needs.</p>
<p>Difficulty involving relevant LGBTIQ+ stakeholder organizations Probability: very low Impact: medium</p>	<p>The partnership includes several LGBTIQ+ organizations, which will facilitate the involvement of relevant LGBTIQ+ stakeholder organizations.</p>
<p>Determining where support is needed in mentoring activities Probability: low Impact: high</p>	<p>It may take a while for the mentors to determine what the mentees need and how to support and encourage them, which could slow the project development. In this case, the mentor can talk to the advisory board or ask the mentee about any shortcomings.</p>

Analytical dimensions

The following analytical dimensions will guide both the quantitative (survey) and qualitative (interviews) phases of the research project, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the needs, perceptions and experiences related to LGBTIQ+ diversity in the workplace.

Training needs

The training needs will be identified through surveys and interviews, focusing on several key dimensions, each encompassing multiple critical areas. The interviews will also offer participants the chance to propose new topics beyond the core themes.

For the training needs of HR professionals and managers in the field of LGBTIQ+ diversity management:

- LGBTIQ+ conceptualization and awareness (training in key concepts, transphobia in the workplace, etc.)
- Workplace experiences and inclusion (personal testimonies from transgender and non-binary individuals, good practice in onboarding processes, etc.)
- Legal rights and protections related to LGBTIQ+ rights and preventing discrimination in the workplace
- Leadership and advocacy for LGBTIQ+ rights in the organization
- Benefits of an inclusive workplace

For trans and non-binary participant needs:

- Legal rights and protections for LGBTIQ+ individuals (specifically transgender/specific legal protection)
- Labour rights and organizations
- Emotional well-being and mental health
- Financial planning and security
- Professional skills and career growth

Experiences (good practices/good experiences versus bad practices/bad experiences)

For the two groups (human resources and trans), both good and bad practices and experiences can foster dialogue that produces insights and guidelines to inform the analysis and be incorporated into the training material.

For human resources professionals and the management group, the following areas will be explored:

- Discrimination observed in the workplace (based on skin colour, age, sexual orientation, etc.)
- Harassment against trans people in the workplace
- Experiences of discrimination during gender transition processes
- Support measures for gender transition processes
- Company practices for trans individuals regarding career growth

For the trans group, the following areas will be explored:

- Openness about being trans or non-binary in their personal and professional lives
- Discrimination observed in the workplace (based on skin colour, age, sexual orientation, etc.)
- Experiences of harassment and violence; to capture varying degrees of harassment, the survey will present examples of situations with escalating levels of severity

- Forms of support when engaged in job searching, as well as support or protection received from various individuals in the workplace

Organizational culture

The aim of this study is to explore how organizations perceive and manage diversity, particularly as it concerns trans individuals. It will focus on determining whether the organization embraces or rejects diversity, as well as the practices and policies related to inclusion. An examination of areas such as equality plans, specific measures for LGBTIQ+ and trans individuals and the workplace climate regarding diversity will obtain a clearer understanding of how these issues are addressed and implemented at the organizational level.

For human resources and management professionals, the following areas will be explored:

- Equality and diversity plans
- LGBTIQ+ and trans-specific measures in the equality plan
- Implementation and effectiveness of policies and measures
- Workplace climate regarding LGBTIQ+ diversity

For the trans group, the following areas will be explored:

- Workplace culture and support for LGBTIQ+ employees
- Protection against discrimination and harassment
- Career advancement and opportunities
- Visibility and representation of LGBTIQ+ individuals

Intersectionality

As outlined in the section on the project's guiding themes, an intersectional approach is fundamental to this project. Sociodemographic information in the following categories will be collected from trans and non-binary respondents: sex assigned at birth, intersex/endosex status, gender identity, sexual orientation, trans visibility, employment status, belonging to other minority groups (skin colour, ethnicity or migrant background, asylum seeker or refugee status, religious minority) and the presence of physical or mental health issues. Additionally, data will be collected on salary ranges, education level, residential area (city/town/rural), employment sector and business size.

The categories for the human resources respondents differ slightly, omitting most of the identity-related data and instead including information on professional roles, years of experience and company classification (ranging from local to international).

While the sociodemographic variables will be collected to capture diverse positionalities, the qualitative component will focus on lived experiences and intersecting forms of discrimination, in an effort to go beyond categorical data to more fully understand how identities shape workplace experiences.

Target groups

Type	Who/Where	Why
Target groups (TG)	HR professionals and managers	Human resources processes seek to optimize employee performance. Strategies can involve teaching employees how to use new technology, rating individual and group performances and using evaluations to develop more efficient processes. HR training and development can also promote the company's culture to create a safe and positive work environment. In addition to advancing employees' careers, the goal of HR training and development is to improve the overall productivity of a company.
	Trans and non-binary individuals	Trans and non-binary people often face discrimination and significant challenges in the workplace due to a lack of awareness, prejudice and negative stereotypes. These factors can impact employment opportunities, career progression and/or salaries and benefits.
	Policymakers	Policymakers must be included in a project aimed at establishing equality for trans people in the workplace due to their role in making legal and policy changes, gaining institutional support, raising public awareness, fostering collaborative decision-making and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project's impact.
Indirect beneficiaries (IB)	LGBTIQ+ community	As a whole, the LGBTIQ+ community often confronts discriminatory behaviours in employment. Training HR professionals and managers can have a positive cascade effect in the enforcement of LGBTIQ+ people's equal rights in the workplace.
Countries directly targeted	European area	The LGBTIQ+ experience of promoting and achieving change and understanding with policymakers and the general population is unsatisfactory or unsuccessful in many EU countries. Those living in environments particularly hostile to LGBTIQ+ people often encounter refusal and obstinacy from public representatives when they try to have their relationships recognised (see ECtHR, <i>Oliari and Others v. Italy</i> , 2015; ECJ, C-673/16 - <i>Coman and O.</i> , 2018), antidiscrimination rules respected (see ECJ, C-81/12, <i>Asociația Accept v. Consiliul Național pentru Combaterea Discriminării</i> , 2013) or even a public space in civil society granted (see ECtHR, <i>Bayev and Others v. Russia</i> , 2017).

Analytical activities timeline

Activity	Apr 25	May 25	Jun 25	Jul. 25	Aug 25	Sep 25	Oct 25	Nov 25	Dec 25	Jan. 26	Feb 26	Mar 26
Final version of the methodology guide	11 th											
Submission for approval to the UdG Research Ethics and Biosecurity Committee	11 th											
Expected approval from the UdG Research Ethics and Biosecurity Committee		26 th										
Submission to the EC (D2.1)	X											
Submission of the standardized interview and survey model to the ECOD2.2	X											
Fieldwork			X	X	X	X	X					
Analysis of training needs (D2.3)							X	X	X			
First summary of the training curriculum									19 th			
Feedback to the summary of the training curriculum										9 th		
First version of the training curriculum											27 th	
Feedback to the summary of the training curriculum (all partners)												6 th
Creating the training curriculum (D2.4)												27 th

Deliverable involved:

D2.1: 1 Methodology guide, English

D2.2: 1 Standardized interview and survey model, English

D2.3: 4 Reports on training needs (1 each country), English, 10 pages

D2.4: 1 Educational plan and tools, including training materials, English

Fieldwork guidelines

These project guidelines are based on the methodology guide developed for the SECY project (funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, Project Number:

PID2023-148567OA-I00). The implementation of the project is subject to evaluation by the University of Girona Research Ethics and Biosafety Committee or another analogous academic committee, if applicable. The researchers are committed to following this guidance and meeting all the ethical requirements throughout the implementation of the project.

The research team will rely on this methodological guide, which includes the protocols and guidelines for each research activity within the project and incorporates the relevant ethical considerations. The main documents related to the ethical aspects of the methodological approach include the following:

- Two interview scripts
- A survey model
- Three informed consent forms for the interviewees:
 - HR and managers
 - Trans and non-binary participants
 - Informed consent form for the institutions employing the professionals interviewed

This study will comply with the ethical standards of social science research. In this regard, all researchers must ensure that every participant receives clear and accessible information about the purpose of the study, the procedures, possible risks or drawbacks, benefits, confidentiality, the right to request additional information and the option to decline or discontinue participation, all communicated in a way that is comprehensible and appropriate to the participant's position and context.

All the researchers will securely store the data collected during the fieldwork according to the data protection plan described in this document. Confidentiality and the pseudonymization of all documents and related data will be ensured. The privacy and anonymity of the participants will be protected throughout the entire research process and for five years after its completion. The researchers involved must be informed about the ethical requirements and ensure full compliance. Misleading information will be avoided at all stages. Biased interpretations or representations of primary data will be avoided.

In the unlikely event that harm or discomfort arises as a result of participating in this study, the researchers will be responsible for ensuring that the participants receive the necessary support and care. All communication related to the study must be completed honestly and transparently, and full, informed consent must be obtained from the participants prior to their involvement.

The results of this study will be publicly available through open-access publications. Additionally, the researchers will ensure that the participants are informed about the findings and invited to the events organized as part of the project. Once the project is completed, the principal investigator will report the results and outcomes to the Ethics Committee.

Data protection

Each partner will manage their files and protect the data according to current national and European laws and regulations in force. All data will be managed in a way that ensures maximum anonymity and the data will be suitably protected. The following documentation will be collected:

- A confidentiality agreement to be signed by the research staff and securely stored by the organization (see Appendixes).
- An informed consent agreement to be signed by the interview participants. In the case of professionals (employed by a company or organization), the legal representatives of said companies will also sign an informed authorization agreement.

The rules for ensuring the best data protection for the implementation of this project are:

- All data used in national or transnational reports, as well as in publications, must be properly coded. It must not be possible to identify any individual participant.
- Audio recordings and transcripts will be coded and securely stored in the institutional account, ensuring that no one outside the project has access to this information.
- Researchers will assess the impact of data protection measures and implement mitigation strategies in the event that any participant might be identifiable due to their particular vulnerability.
- Data may be collected and processed as long as it is appropriate, relevant and not excessive for the purposes of the project (8 years). Unnecessary data will be avoided.
- Special category data (ethnic or racial origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, union membership, genetic data, biometric data intended to uniquely identify a natural person, health, sex life, sexual orientation, etc.) require the adoption of special security measures and should only be processed when necessary.

- Pseudonymization is a fundamental technique for mitigating data protection risks. EU law defines pseudonymization as the processing of personal data in such a way that it can no longer be attributed to a specific individual without the use of additional information.
- Storage information must always be managed through the institutional platforms that ensure legal compliance regarding data protection and security (for example, personal file and management spaces will be avoided). In this regard, researchers will work with anonymized or pseudonymized documents, storing the dataset document containing the identification, as well as the consent forms or documentation containing identifying data, in a location with restricted and limited access (for example, a storage space to which they have no access, access is protected by passwords, and/or the data is encrypted).

Interviews

Recruitment

When selecting stakeholders to be interviewed, it will be important to strike a balance between including individuals with diverse perspectives and ensuring that the selected stakeholders have the necessary expertise and knowledge to provide meaningful insights for the training needs analysis. The following selection criteria will be used to identify suitable stakeholders for the interviews: 1) diversity of roles in the organization and experience (position, years of experience); 2) organizational context (organization size, sector, location, etc.); and 3) experience with trans issues.

For the interviews with transgender and non-binary participants, the following selection criteria will be considered: 1) an inclusive spectrum, including participants with different self-identification; 2) employment status (currently employed or unemployed; formal/informal sectors; full-time/part-time/freelance; 3) diversity regarding job searches pre-, during and post-transition; 4) sociodemographic diversity (age, education level, geographic diversity, administrative status, etc.).

The interviewers should begin by approaching people already known to them and/or individuals who may act as facilitators to other participants, as access to the field is often laborious and time-consuming. However, the replication of exclusions should be avoided by actively recruiting beyond mainstream circles (avoiding, for example, only White, able-bodied, cisgender or similar professional roles and organizations). An email will introduce the interviewers, with information about the project attached and specific information about the

interview (it will be conducted by the writer, be audio recorded and should take about 1 hour). The interviewee can be met where and when it is most suitable for them.

Note 1: At least 10 interviews are expected per participant country (TG), with over 50 per cent of the interviews conducted with transgender and non-binary people.

Note 2: All participants must be of legal age.

Note 3: For interviews with professionals, the consent of both the interviewed professional and the organization they work for must be secured.

Interview Protocol

The interviews will be audio recorded and conducted according to a semi-structured script, as long as the participant agrees. They must be conducted in a quiet place, with minimum interruption and no risk of being overheard, as that may produce constraints. They can be conducted in person or online. The average duration of each interview should be 50-60 minutes.

Pre-interview checklist

- Audio recorder and batteries with sufficient memory space
- Pen and paper
- Interview script (included in this methodological guide)
- Documents: consent form (see Appendixes)

Pre-interview rapport

Before beginning the interview, the interviewer will seek informed consent from the interviewee, explaining the project's objectives, risks and data protection rules. The interviewer will explain that the interviewee will be asked to respond to questions on their own terms. The interviewer will say that if the interviewee wishes to stop the interview at any time, they can. The interviewer will ask the interviewee if they have any questions about this and will answer these questions before moving on to start the interview. In order to protect the personal data of the interviewees, the informed consent will not collect the names of participants, only the signatures. Signed informed consent forms need to be stored in a safe place with access restricted to staff directly involved in the project. After this, or at the end of the interview, the interviewee will be asked to sign a consent form, which states that they are willing to take part in the research project.

Starting the interview

- Mobile phones should be switched off.
- The interviewer should ensure that the audio recorder is working and note the name/category of the person being interviewed as well as the date (e.g. 'Interview conducted by [name], on [day/month/year]').
- Each interview will start with the interviewee being thanked for their participation, followed by the first question in the script. The conversation may then flow organically, and the order of questions may differ from the script. During this process, the interviewer should be aware of the time and ensure that all the topics in the script are being covered.

Important tip: The role of the interviewer is to facilitate the conversation, not to comment on what is being said. The interviewer's body language should create a welcoming interview environment.

Important: If it is possible that asking for or recording any personal data (legal status, transgender or cisgender identity, etc.) could put the participant at risk or compromise the future anonymization of their data, this information does not have to be collected. Additionally, participants have the right to decline to answer any questions during the interview, including those in the data collection section.

After the interview

The interviewer should ensure that the interview has been recorded correctly and the data stored in a secure location with access limited to authorized persons. If the interview was not recorded upon the request of the interviewee, an extensive report of the interview should be written up and the interview transcribed as accurately as possible. All the data in a transcribed interview must be anonymized to prevent recognition of the interviewee. Transcriptions should be done as soon as possible after the recording, as the audio recordings will be destroyed immediately after the interviews are transcribed and anonymized. Only researchers directly related to the project will have access to the interview transcriptions.

Each interviewee will be assigned a code. Interviews with transgender and non-binary participants will be coded 'TNB', followed by a number in the order of recording (TNB1, TNB2, TNB3, etc.). Interviews with human resources professionals and managers will be coded 'HRM', followed by a number in the order of recording (HRM1, HRM2, HRM3, etc.). If the interviewers

choose to maintain a list that links the interviewees' names to their assigned codes, this list will be encrypted and stored in a separate folder with restricted access, ideally limited to one individual not directly involved in the research phase.

Interview script for trans and non-binary participants

Introduction

This interview forms part of a two-year research project called *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace*, conducted by a consortium of universities and civil society organizations from Bulgaria, Italy, Lithuania and Spain. The project is co-funded by the European Union. The aim of the project is to promote the inclusion of transgender and non-binary people in the workplace by improving the skills of human resources professionals, raising awareness and supporting trans individuals through mentoring programmes.

This interview will focus specifically on your experiences as a transgender or non-binary person, especially regarding your access to work and your personal experience in the labour market.

You control the interview. You can choose to stop it at any time or skip any question you don't feel like answering. There is no need to explain and there won't be any consequences. Feel free to answer in your own words and only share what you're comfortable with. The information you share will be kept strictly confidential. No names or identifying information will appear in any report or publication.

This interview may bring up some sensitive or challenging topics for you. If at any point you feel uncomfortable or upset, you are welcome to pause or end the conversation whenever you need to.

Even though taking part in this project will not directly benefit you, the information you share is very important to help us better understand the challenges people face at work and how to make workplaces more inclusive. The results of this study will be shared anonymously in reports and publications and at events to help raise awareness and advocate positive change.

With your permission, we would like to audio record this interview, as it would be extremely helpful for the analysis and accuracy of our research. Do we have your consent to record?

Thank you for your time and willingness to share your experiences.

A. Sociodemographic data

To begin, before discussing your experiences in the workplace, we would like to ask you a few questions about your background. These questions will help us understand the diversity of experiences and perspectives of the people participating in this study.

A.1 What year were you born?

A.2 What country were you born in? [If applicable, what was the reason for migrating?]

A.3 What is your legal status? (Prompt: citizen, permanent or temporary resident, undocumented)

A.4 What gender do you identify with? Are you a transgender or non-binary person?

A.5 How long have you identified as X? And when did you first come out?

A.6 Would you say you are cis passing?

A.7 What sexual orientation do you define yourself by?

A.8 What is your highest completed education level?

A.9 How would you describe your overall physical and mental health?

A.10 Do you consider yourself neurotypical or neurodivergent? (If neurodivergent, could you specify the type?)

A. 11 Who do you live with? Do you live in a town or a city (and how big is it)? Would you describe it as a rural or an urban environment? [Note down the region if relevant for the national team]

A.12 What do you do for a living? [Specifically regarding financial subsistence] *Identify if the person works where they live.*

A11 What sector do you work in?

B. Experiences

We'd now like to ask about how open you are regarding your gender identity in different areas of your life. These questions aim to determine the social and professional contexts in which you feel comfortable being visible as a trans/non-binary person.

B.1 In your everyday life, who are you open with about being trans/nonbinary?

B.2 Are you open about your gender identity at your workplace? With whom? (Prompt: work colleagues, immediate superior/head of department, customers, clients, etc.)

Experiences of discrimination and support at work

Now we would like to focus on gender identity in the workplace. Trans and non-binary people often face specific forms of discrimination or exclusion at work. These questions aim to better understand how your gender identity may have shaped your experiences in professional settings, not just in your current work environment, but in any past or present jobs, even if you are currently unemployed.

B.3 How has your gender identity influenced your experience in the workplace?

B.4 Thinking about your daily interactions at work, have there been situations where you felt overlooked, dismissed or treated differently, even in ways that may have seemed subtle or unintentional? Could you describe how these experiences impacted you?

B.5 Can you describe any specific situations – whether minor or significant – where your gender identity led to inappropriate behaviour, microaggressions or biased treatment? (Prompt: Were there any specific comments, jokes or tones that made you feel uncomfortable?)

B.6 Have you ever been the target of violence or harassment at work because you are transgender or non-binary, or because your gender expression does not follow gender roles? (If yes: What happened? How did the situation unfold?)

B.7 Would you say that these kinds of experiences are isolated incidents or part of a recurring pattern in your workplace? Can you provide examples? (Prompt: Do you feel that harassment or discrimination based on gender identity is normalized or tolerated in any way?)

B.8 How did the incidents affect your health and well-being? (Prompt: short-term/long-term)

B.9 *If the person mentioned a specific episode, ask about it:* With the situation you described, did you decide to report it to your organization? What influenced your decision to do so, or why did you decide not to?

B.10 (If B9 = 'Yes') What was your experience like when you decided to report the matter to your organization?

B.11 Did you receive any support during this incident? From whom? (Prompt: the company, co-workers, family, friends, personal network) How did they support you?

Experiences when transitioning at work

B.12 Did you undergo any part of your gender transition while employed? If so, could you please describe your experiences?

Experiences of discrimination when looking for a job

B.13 In the last five years, how many times have you changed your workplace? If so, why?

B.14 Could you tell us about your experience looking for a job? (If applicable, in the case of changing jobs or being unemployed)

B.15 (If B.13 = 'Yes') Can you describe any forms of financial support you received while looking for a job? This could include support from institutions, your family or informal networks. How did these resources help you during your job search?

B.16 What are the main obstacles you have faced in the job market?

C. Training needs

Now we'd like to talk about your professional development. Building a career often involves developing certain skills or gaining access to specific resources. These questions aim to better understand what you feel you need – or would have needed – to grow or advance in your work life, whether in your current role, a previous job or while looking for employment.

C.1 What skills do you think you need to enhance your job possibilities?

C.2 What training would you need in terms of...?

Methodological note: *Interviewers should consider the following areas during this part of the interview: labour rights, trans-specific legal rights and protections, emotional self-protection, CV building and writing, networking strategies, job search strategies, interviewing skills. The response should contain as much detail as can be elicited. Please try to avoid simple 'Yes/No' answers and talk about the specific training or support the interviewee feels would be most helpful for them in these areas. In particular:*

- Encourage the interviewee to provide examples or specific situations where their needs were supported.
- Ask follow-up questions to clarify or dive deeper into any of the topics mentioned.
- Determine their specific training needs and challenges in each of the areas listed.

C.3 In your experience, what kind of training do companies need to improve gender diversity at work?

Methodological note: Interviewers should consider the following areas when asking: organization policies, opportunities for career growth and leadership for minorities, knowledge about sexual and gender diversity, preventing gender discrimination, creating a more inclusive work environment.

C.4 What do trans employees need in order to improve their experience and opportunities in the workplace?

Methodological note: Interviewers should consider the following topics when asking: job access, job improvement, skills, abilities.

D. Organizational culture

D.1 How important is transgender and non-binary inclusivity in your organization? Is it promoted?

D.2 What do you think about your organization's policies and overall corporate culture in terms of preventing violence and dismissive language/behaviour against transgender and non-binary people?

D.3 Have you felt any pressure to conform to workplace norms that don't align with your identity? How? Can you provide examples?

D.4 How would you describe your experience in terms of being recognized and advancing in your work environment compared to your colleagues?

D.5 Are transgender and non-binary people involved in decision-making processes when it comes to policies that affect their well-being? How?

Interview script for human resources and management professionals

Introduction

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this interview, which is part of the *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace* research project. The project is co-funded by the European Union, and conducted by a consortium of universities and civil society organizations from Bulgaria, Italy, Lithuania and Spain. The aim of the project is to promote the inclusion of transgender and non-binary people in the workplace by improving the skills of human resources professionals, raising awareness about the challenges they face and developing mentoring programs to support trans and non-binary individuals.

This interview will focus specifically on your experiences as a human resources or management professional, particularly regarding diversity management and the inclusion of transgender and non-binary individuals in the workplace.

Even though taking part in this project may not have a direct impact in your context, the information you share is very important to help us better understand the challenges people face at work and how to make workplaces more inclusive. The results of this study will be shared anonymously in reports and publications and at events to help raise awareness and advocate positive change.

You are free to stop the interview or skip any question at any time. There is no need to explain and there won't be any consequences. Your well-being is a priority, and you can pause or end the conversation at any point if you feel uncomfortable.

With your permission, we would like to audio record this interview, as it would be extremely helpful for the analysis and accuracy of our research. Do we have your consent to record?

A. Sociodemographic data

To begin, before discussing your experiences in your role, we would like to ask you a few questions about your background. These questions will help us understand the diversity of experiences and perspectives of people who participate in this study.

A.1 What year were you born?

A.2 What gender do you identify with?

A.3 What is your highest completed education level?

A.4 What is your current professional role?

A.5 How many years of experience do you have in this sector?

A.6 What sector does your organization operate in?

A.7 How many employees work at your workplace?

A.8 Is your organization local, regional, national or international?

B. Experiences

Now, we'd like to ask you about the visibility and experiences of transgender and non-binary individuals in your organization.

B.1 Can you tell us about the presence or visibility of transgender or non-binary individuals within your organization?

B.2. Can you recall any instance where you witnessed violence, harassment or dismissive comments or behaviour toward someone who is transgender or non-binary at work? Please describe what happened.

B.3 How did the organization handle the incident? Who supported whom?

B4. Can you describe your experience navigating transgender and non-binary issues in your organization?

B5. Has anyone in your organization undergone a gender transition while in their role? How did this experience affect the workplace, both in terms of daily operations and the overall environment? What challenges did the company face or what positive changes did you see, and how did colleagues and management respond?

C. Training needs

Now, we'd like to focus on training and development needs related to gender diversity and inclusion. These questions explore your experience with training, identify gaps and discussing what skills and knowledge could better support transgender and non-binary individuals in the workplace.

C.1 Have you ever been involved in or organized any training or courses on gender diversity or LGBTIQ+ issues? If so, what topics were covered and what was your overall impression of the experience? How did the staff respond to it and, in your view, what impact did it have on them?

C.2 Have you had any experience with training aimed at integrating inclusive practices, particularly for trans or non-binary individuals, into your daily work? If so, what was the focus of the training, and what insights or changes did it bring, either for you or the team? *Inclusive practices might include using correct names and pronouns, providing access to gender-neutral facilities, updating administrative systems to reflect chosen names, offering gender diversity training, or having clear protocols against discrimination.*

C.3 If you have not been involved in such training, do you think it would be beneficial for you or your staff to engage in training on gender diversity or the rights of trans and non-binary individuals? What do you think would motivate or discourage staff from participating in such a course?

C.4 What skills and competencies do you believe are essential for leadership teams and HR professionals to improve career development opportunities for transgender and non-binary individuals in the workplace?

C.5 How would you rate the current understanding of gender diversity and non-binary identities within your leadership team and HR department? What additional knowledge do you think is essential to support transgender and non-binary employees effectively?

C.6 What recruitment strategies or skills do you think HR professionals need to ensure that transgender and non-binary candidates have equal access to job opportunities?

C.7 What kind of training or awareness programmes do you believe are necessary for HR professionals and leadership to foster a more inclusive workplace for transgender and non-binary people?

C.8 What skills do HR and leadership teams need to better recognize and reduce the unconscious bias that may affect the careers of transgender and non-binary employees?

C.9 What communication skills are essential for HR and leadership teams when interacting with transgender and non-binary employees to ensure respect and inclusivity?

C.10 What skills do HR professionals need to develop to effectively support transgender and non-binary employees in their career development?

C.11 What knowledge or skills should HR professionals have regarding legal protections and inclusive workplace policies for transgender and non-binary individuals?

C.12 What leadership skills are required to effectively advocate for the inclusion of transgender and non-binary individuals in the workplace? How can leaders be role models for inclusivity?

C.13 What do transgender employees need to improve their experience and opportunities in the workplace?

D. Organizational culture

D.1 What do you think about inclusive policies in organizations in general?

D.2 Has your organization enacted diversity, equity and inclusion policies? Do they include sexual orientation as a protected characteristic? Do they include gender identity/gender expression as protected characteristics? Do they include actions for the inclusion of trans and/or non-binary persons?

D.3 (If D2 = 'Yes') Could you briefly describe these policies? What are the main reasons for adopting these policies? Do you think that they are sufficient? Are these policies applied consistently and fairly in practice? Why/why not?

D.4 What is your policy/practice, if any, regarding transition: name change, communication with employees, bathroom and changing-room usage, etc.

D.5 (If D2 = 'No') What are the main reasons for not adopting these policies? Are there any relevant actions/measures that you would suggest? If yes, which ones? If not, why?

D.6 Are your recruitment policies trans, intersex and non-binary inclusive? If yes, could you please describe them? If not, how can recruitment policies be adapted in order to be inclusive?

D.7 In your experience, how common are jokes or comments that target transgender people in your workplace? Tell us more if you witnessed something of that sort and what was the work dynamic.

D.8 Do you feel that the employees in your company are assumed to be heterosexual? How do you think this assumption affects the work environment or the experiences of those who don't fit this norm?

D.9 Are trans/non binary people in middle or high management or executive positions?

D.10 How do you think your co-workers would respond if a transgender person were in a leadership position?

D.11 What forms of support do you think would be most effective in helping trans and non-binary employees advance in their careers within the organization?

D.12 How inclusive do you think your organization's social events and team-building activities are for transgender and non-binary individuals, in terms of both the language used in invitations and the kinds of activities planned?

D.13 Please give examples of any company activities, campaigns and/or workshops implemented to help you build a more inclusive work environment for transgender and non-binary people.

D.14 How does the leadership team in your organization actively support LGBTIQ+ employees, both publicly and privately?

Survey

Target groups

- HR professionals and managers
- Trans and non-binary individuals
- LGBTIQ+ individuals (as indirect beneficiaries of the overall project, their responses will provide valuable insights into the broader LGBTIQ+ experience in the workplace, enabling a specific comparison with the unique experiences of trans and non-binary individuals, a distinction that will broaden the general understanding of the different challenges and needs each group faces related to workplace dynamics)

Survey design and implementation

LimeSurvey software will be used to create the online questionnaire, incorporating both multiple-choice and open-ended questions. This approach will: a) provide easy access to the survey via a link generated by the software; b) ensure anonymous, consistent and voluntary data collection; c) centralize the recording of responses; and d) facilitate the sharing of results amongst the partners. The initial survey will be written in English, before being translated into the local languages. A single survey will be used for all the target groups, with a specific question directing participants to their relevant sub-survey.

Note 1: The survey requires a minimum of 400 responses, with each partner expected to secure at least 100 participants. Of these, at least 50 should come from the HR group and 50 from the LGBTIQ+ group. Within the LGBTIQ+ group, a minimum of 35 participants should be transgender or non-binary. To ensure a robust statistical analysis, a higher response rate is strongly encouraged.

Note 2: Only fully completed surveys will be included in the final count.

Note 3: All participants must be of legal age.

Survey recruitment and dissemination strategies

For the HR and management recruitment, the consortium will follow the guidance of the European Association for Local Democracy (ALDA), a project partner. The survey will be sent to international and national organizations and cover a wide range of sectors.

In order to recruit trans and non-binary participants, each project partner will collaborate with national non-governmental organizations, trans rights advocacy groups and public institutions that provide services to trans communities. To enhance outreach and response rates within this target group, the dissemination strategy will include the involvement of community leaders and activists with a strong online presence, whose engagement is expected to foster wider visibility and trust within the community.

Survey model

Project title: *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace*

This survey forms part of the European project Transcending barriers, that aims to promote the inclusion of trans people in the workplace. The survey is addressed to:

- Human Resources and management professionals
- Transgender and non-binary individuals
- Lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual, and intersex people.

There is currently little data on the employment situation of trans and non-binary people in the participant countries. While your participation in the survey may not have a direct impact in your context, it can contribute to progress for the trans and non-binary community. It takes around 15-20 minutes to complete the questionnaire. There are no right or wrong answers; what matters most is your honest experience and opinion.

Your responses will be anonymous and confidential. No personal data will be collected. All information will be securely stored and analysed by Glas Foundation (Bulgaria), Università degli Studi di Brescia (Italy), Vytautas Magnus University (Lithuania) and Universitat de Girona (Spain), which are responsible for data collecting, processing, and storage.

For questions, contact: [add national contact information]. The principal investigators are: [add name of the national team leader]. Data confidentiality and protection complies with Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Your participation is completely voluntary and you may exit the survey at any time without any consequences. The results will be shared anonymously with the scientific community and the general public.

Some questions may bring up difficult experiences. You may skip any question or stop if needed. The national organisation of the country you live in is responsible for addressing any discomfort or distress that may result from your participation in this study. If you experience any such effects and need additional support, you can contact the following: [add institutional email address]

This survey is part of a two-year action-research project funded by the European Union. It is led by an international team from universities and organizations in Bulgaria, Italy, Lithuania, and Spain. Based on the findings from this research, training sessions for Human Resources professionals and mentoring programs to support trans individuals will be developed in each country.

We greatly appreciate your time and collaboration. Please click 'Next' to confirm your participation.

Consent

Do you agree to take part in this research?

1. Yes
2. No

Target question 1

Are you...?

1. A Human Resources professional or manager in an organization
2. Transgender or non-binary
3. Lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual, intersex

If respondent selects the first option, the survey for human resources professionals will open. If respondent selects the second option, the survey for transgender, non-binary, lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual and intersex individuals will open. If respondent falls into both groups (professional+ LGBTIQA+), the following comment will show:

It looks like you belong to more than one of our target groups —as a Human Resources professional or manager; and as a trans, non-binary or LGBIA person. Thank you for participating! You will now be directed to the Human Resources section of the survey, as we are particularly interested in your professional insights and feedback.)

Target question 2

Have you worked during the last 5 years, whether with or without a work contract?

1. Yes
2. No

Survey for transgender, non-binary, lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual and intersex individuals

We'll now ask you a few questions about your background. This helps us better understand the diversity of experiences and perspectives among participants.

G1. Sociodemographic data

G1Q1. Which country do you currently live in?

1. Bulgaria
2. Italy
3. Lithuania
4. Spain
5. Other: _____

G1Q2. What year were you born?

[Year selection 1956-2007]

G1Q3. Which term identifies you best? *If your gender identity isn't listed, please choose the option that most closely represents you.*

1. Trans woman
2. Trans man
3. Non-binary
4. Cisgender
5. Prefer not to say
6. Other: _____

G1Q4. What sex were you assigned at birth?

1. Male
2. Female
3. Other: _____
4. Prefer not to say

G1Q5. Are you an intersex person? *intersex individuals are born with sex characteristics (sexual anatomy, reproductive organs, hormonal structure and/or levels and/or chromosomal patterns) that do not fit the typical definition of male or female. The term "intersex" is an umbrella term for the spectrum of variations of sex characteristics that naturally occur within the human species. The term intersex acknowledges the fact that physically, sex is a spectrum and that people with variations of sex characteristics other than male or female exist. ILGA-Europe Glossary*

1. Yes
2. No
3. I don't know
4. I prefer not to answer

G1Q6. Would you say you are... *Please select the one answer that fits you best. If your sexual orientation isn't listed, please choose the option that most closely represents you.*

1. Gay
2. Lesbian
3. Bisexual
4. Heterosexual/straight
5. Asexual
6. Don't know
7. Prefer not to say

G1Q7. (If TQ1=2) Would you say that you are perceived as cis by others? *A cis (cisgender) person is someone whose gender identity aligns with their sex assigned at birth*

1. Not at all
2. A little
3. Somewhat
4. Quite
5. Fully
6. I prefer not to say

G1Q8. Which of the following best describes your status? *You can select more than one option*

1. In a salaried job with a formal contract (including temporary leaves)
2. Self-employed
3. Working outside of the legal system
4. Unemployed
5. Doing unpaid or voluntary work
6. Retired
7. Student
8. Otherwise not working (e.g. taking care of home, on a long sick leave, disabled):

9. Prefer not to say

G1Q8b. (When G1Q8= 1 or 2) Is your main job in the public or the private sector?

Companies with public ownership but private management and working conditions should be considered part of the private sector in this survey.

1. Public sector (administration, public services, state-owned companies)
2. Private (private companies)
3. Third sector (NGOs, associations, foundations, non-profit cooperatives)
4. Prefer not to say
5. Other:

G1Q9. What is your approximate annual salary (before taxes)? [The question needs to be adapted to each national context]

1. -20%
2. -20% -20%
3. 20% -20%
4. -20%- statutory minimum wage
5. Statutory minimum wage- +20%
6. +20% +20%
7. +20% +20%
8. +20% +20%
9. +20% +20%
10. < +20%
11. Prefer not to say

Example: The statutory minimum wage in Spain in 2025 is 16575€

1. Less than €8,500
2. €8,500- €11,000
3. €11,000-€13,000
4. €13,000-€16,500
5. €16,500-€20,000
6. €20,000-€24,000
7. €24,000-€29,000
8. €29,000-€34,000
9. €34,000-€41,000
10. More than more than €41,000
11. Prefer not to say

G1Q10. In the country where you live, do you consider yourself to be part of any of the following groups? *Please select all that apply*

1. A minority in terms of skin colour or ethnicity
2. A minority in terms of migrant background
3. Asylum seeker or refugee
4. A religious minority
5. A person with a disability
6. None of the above
7. Don't know
8. Prefer not to say
9. Another minority group: _____

G1Q11. How would you describe your overall health?

Subquestions:

1. Physical Health
2. Mental Health

Answers:

1. Very Bad	2. Poor	3. Fair	4. Good	5. Excellent	6. I prefer not to answer
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G1Q12. What is your highest completed educational level? [Translate according to each national educational system based on the International Standard Classification of Education] *Choose one of the following answers*

1. Early childhood education ('less than primary' for educational attainment)
2. Primary education

3. Lower secondary education
4. Upper secondary education
5. Post-secondary non-tertiary education
6. Short-cycle tertiary education
7. Bachelor's or equivalent level
8. Master's or equivalent level
9. Doctorate or equivalent level
10. I prefer not to say

G1Q13. Where do you currently live? [Translate adapting to each national context; keep the population numbers]

1. Big city (more than 1,000,000 inhabitants)
2. Medium-size city (between 100,000 and 1,000,000 inhabitants)
3. Town (fewer than 100,000 inhabitants)
4. City suburbs or outskirts
5. Rural village
6. Farm or home in the countryside
7. I prefer not to say

G1Q14. What sector do you work in? (If G1Q8= 1,2 or 3)

1. Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing
2. Arts and Entertainment
3. Cleaning
4. Care services
5. Construction and Manufacturing
6. Education and Training
7. Executive and Government Leadership
8. Finance and Insurance services
9. Hair and Beauty industry
10. Healthcare and Social Work
11. Technology (ICT)
12. Media and Communications
13. Nonprofit work in an NGO, policy and advocacy
14. Professional services (legal, consulting, accounting)
15. Public Administration and Government
16. Shop salesperson
17. Sex work
18. Transportation and Logistics
19. Waiter and Tourism services
20. I prefer not to say
21. Other: _____

G1Q15. (If G1Q8= 1,2 or 3) How many employees work at your workplace?

1. Less than 5
2. Between 5 and 20
3. 21-50
4. 51-100
5. 101-500
6. More than 500
7. Non applicable
8. I prefer not to answer

G2. Experiences

We'll now ask about experiences of discrimination or inappropriate behaviour and experiences of support you may have had. Some questions may touch on sensitive topics. Feel free to skip any question you're not comfortable answering.

G2Q1a. (If TQ1=2) Have you come out to anyone as a trans or non-binary person?

1. Yes
2. No

G2Q1a2. (If TQ1=3) Have you come out to anyone as LGBTIQ+?

1. Yes
2. No

G2Q1b. (If TQ1=2) At what age did you first come out as a trans or non-binary person?

List [1-90]

G2Q1b2. (If TQ1=3) At what age did you first come out as a LGBTIQ+?

List [1-90]

G2Q2a. (If TQ1=2) From the following groups, with how many people are you open about yourself being trans or non-binary?

Subquestions:

1. Friends
2. Neighbours
3. Family
4. Online networks followers
5. Work colleagues Immediate superior/head of department
6. Customers, clients, etc., at work.

7. Professional network or industry peers

Answers:

1. Non	2. A few	3. Some	4. Most	5. All	6. Not applicable
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G2Q2b. (If TQ1=3) From the following groups, with how many people are you open about yourself being LGBTQIA+?

Subquestions:

1. Friends
2. Neighbours
3. Family
4. Online networks followers
5. Work colleagues Immediate superior/head of department
6. Customers, clients, etc., at work.
7. Professional network or industry peers

G2Q3a. (If G1Q8= 1,2,3,5) For each of the following types of discrimination, please indicate to what extent you believe it occurs in your workplace or work environment.

Subquestions:

1. Skin colour
2. Ethnic origin
3. Migrant background
4. Nationality
5. Gender
6. Age
7. Gender identity
8. Sexual orientation
9. Religion or belief
10. Disability
11. Social class or economic status
12. Physical appearance
13. Weight or body size
14. Mental health

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q3b. (If G1Q8=4,6,7) For each of the following types of discrimination, please indicate to what extent you believe it occurs in your last workplace experience

Subquestions:

1. Skin colour

2. Ethnic origin
3. Migrant background
4. Nationality
5. Gender
6. Age
7. Gender identity
8. Sexual orientation
9. Religion or belief
10. Disability
11. Social class or economic status
12. Physical appearance
13. Weight or body size
14. Mental health

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q4. (If TQ2=1) Over the past five years, to what extent have you experienced the following types of harassment in your workplace or work environment?

Subquestions:

1. Name calling, such as personal attacks or insults
2. Mobbing
3. Ridiculing (making jokes about you)
4. Other verbal insult/abuse/humiliation
5. Other non-verbal insult, abuse, humiliation (such as text or images)
6. Excessive/constant negative comments
7. Spreading rumours or lies
8. Aggressive gestures (such as pointing)
9. Isolation from something or somebody; ignoring

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q5. (If TQ2=1) Over the past five years, to what extent have you experienced the following types of violence in your workplace or work environment?

Subquestions

1. Destroying/ stealing personal belongings
2. Striking doors or objects
3. Using physical force to intimidate or control
4. Using a weapon or object to intimidate or harm

5. Grabbing
6. Pushing
7. Hitting
8. Making explicit sexual remarks
9. Someone watched you in an intimate situation without your consent (e.g., in a changing room or toilet)
10. Exposing oneself or making obscene gestures
11. Non-consensual physical contact (e.g., groping or inappropriate touching)
12. You have been followed in explicit by work-related individuals in an intrusive or intimidating manner
13. Unsolicited sharing of sexually explicit material
14. Unwanted sexual advances
15. Rape

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q6. (If TQ2=1) In the last five years, to what extent have you experienced any of the following situations in your day-to-day work life because you are, or are perceived as transgender, non-binary, lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual or intersex?

Subquestions:

1. You have been treated with less respect than other people
2. People have acted as if they thought you were not intelligent
3. People have been avoiding you
4. People have acted as if they thought you were untrustworthy
5. People have acted as if they were better than you

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q7. In the last five years, how many times have you changed workplaces?

1. Never
2. 1 time
3. 2 times
4. 3 times
5. 4 times
6. 5 or more times

G2Q8. (If G2Q7 is anything other than 'Never'). When you have been looking for a job, have you received any of the following forms of support?

Subquestions:

1. Government unemployment benefits
2. Financial support from family members
3. Support from friends or personal network
4. Assistance from NGOs or charities
5. Severance pays from a former employer
6. Savings or personal emergency funds
7. Loans or financial aid (bank, credit unions, microloans, etc.)

Answers:

1.Never	2.Rarely	3.Sometimes	4.Often	5.Always	6.Not applicable
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G2Q9. (If TQ2=1) During your employment in the last 5 years, have any of the following groups supported you, defended or protected you and your rights as transgender, non-binary, lesbian, gay, bisexual, asexual or intersex at work?

Subquestions:

1. Work colleagues
2. Immediate superior/head of department
3. Human resources professionals
4. Customers, clients, etc., at work
5. Professional network or industry peers
6. Trade Union, labor union, staff committee

Answers:

None	A few	Some	Most	All	Not applicable
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G2Q10. (If TQ1=2) During your employment in the last 5 years, have you undergone a gender affirmation process?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I prefer not to answer

G2Q11 (If G2Q.10= 1) To what extent have you experienced the following situations during your gender affirmation process in your workplace or work environment?

Subquestions:

1. Rejection or discriminatory attitudes from colleagues or supervisors
2. Inappropriate comments or invasive questions about your gender affirmation process

3. Changes in how colleagues treat you after coming out
4. Opposition from management or human resources
5. Difficulties in changing your name and gender in the company's internal Systems
6. Use of the wrong pronouns
7. Use of your old name
8. Issues or resistance from co-workers regarding restroom or changing room use
9. Changes in how your professional skills are perceived after transitioning
10. Discrimination in promotions or project assignments
11. Being reassigned to a non-customer-facing role without you requesting for it
12. Loss of your job

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionaly	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G2Q12 (If G2Q.10=1) To what extent have you experienced the following situations during your gender affirmation process at your workplace or work environment?

Subquestions:

1. Acceptance and correct use of your name and pronouns
2. Support and understanding from co-workers
3. Company support in updating official documentation
4. Availability of internal resources (diversity committee, LGBTIQ+ support groups)
5. Access to restrooms and changing rooms that align with your gender identity
6. Changes in dress codes or uniforms to match your gender identity
7. Improved well-being and confidence after living authentically
8. Feeling of belonging after coming out

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionaly	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G3. Training needs

If TQ2=1: *The next question aims to explore what you need — or may have needed — to grow in your work life, whether in a job or while looking for one.*

If TQ2=2: *This is the final question. It aims to explore what you need — or may have needed — to grow in your work life, whether in a job or while looking for one.*

G3Q1. Do you think that you need training in... *If you're already informed or have this competence, you can select 'unnecessary' or 'strongly unnecessary'.*

Subquestions:

1. Laws related to LGBTIQ+ rights
2. Transgender-specific legal rights and protections
3. Labour rights
4. Labour union organizations
5. LGBTIQ+, Trans and Non-binary organisations
6. Emotional self-protection
7. Mental health and well-being
8. Dealing with subtle discrimination at work
9. Financial planning and security during a gender affirmation process
10. Public speaking and advocacy for LGBTI rights
11. CV building and résumé writing
12. Enhancing professional skills for career growth
13. Networking strategies
14. Building a personal brand and online presence
15. Job search strategies
16. Interviewing skills
17. Handling questions about your gender identity from colleagues, supervisors, or during hiring processes
18. Learning leadership skills and management training for career progression

Answers:

Strongly unnecessary	Unnecessary	Neither necessary nor unnecessary	Necessary	Strongly necessary	Unsure / Don't know
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G4. Organizational culture

This is the final question. It aims to understand whether LGBTIQ+ inclusion is part of the culture in your current or past workplace.

G4Q1. Answer the following...

Subquestions:

1. Do you feel that your organization promotes a culture of respect and safety for LGBTI people?
2. How important is LGBTI diversity in your organization?
3. Does your organization have specific policies or protocols to protect LGBTI people from discrimination, harassment or violence?
4. Has your organisation provided its employees with any training or workshops specifically about LGBTIQ+ issues or gender identity?

5. To what extent do you believe LGBTIQ+ employees have equal opportunities for advancement and career growth compared to other employees in your organization?
6. To what extent has your organization celebrated or acknowledged LGBTIQ+ Pride Month, Transgender Day of Visibility, or similar events?
7. To what extent do you see LGBTIQ+-related topics addressed in company communications (e.g., newsletters, internal emails, public campaigns)?
8. Do you believe that LGBTIQ+ employees are involved in decision-making processes, especially when it comes to policies that affect their well-being?
9. Do you feel that the leadership in your organization actively supports LGBTIQ+ employees, both publicly and privately?
10. Leadership positions within the organisation include people who are openly trans or non-binary

Answers:

Not at all	A little	Somehow	Quite	Totally	Unsure/ I don't know	Not applicable
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END

Thank you for your time. The results of the survey will be published at the end of the research phase. If you know anyone who might be interested in participating, please feel free to share the link. We especially encourage trans and non-binary individuals to take part in the survey. If you would like to share your experience in an interview, or if you would like to receive updates on the implementation of the Transcending Barriers project, you can contact the research team of the country you live in, at: [add partner's email]

Survey for human resources professionals and managers

G5. Sociodemographic data

G5Q1. Which country do you currently live in?

1. Bulgaria
2. Italy
3. Lithuania
4. Spain
5. Other: _____

G5Q2. What year were you born?

[Year selection 1945-2007]

G5Q3. Do you identify as...?

1. Female
2. Male
3. Non-binary
4. Prefer not to say
5. Other: _____

G5Q4. What is your highest completed educational level? [Translate according to each national educational system based on the International Standard Classification of Education] *Choose one of the following answers*

1. Early childhood education ('less than primary' for educational attainment)
2. Primary education
3. Lower secondary education
4. Upper secondary education
5. Post-secondary non-tertiary education
6. Short-cycle tertiary education
7. Bachelor's or equivalent level
8. Master's or equivalent level
9. Doctorate or equivalent level
10. I prefer not to say

G5Q5. What is your current professional role?

1. Human Resources Manager
2. Human Resources Generalist
3. Human Resources Administrator
4. Human Resources Business Partner
5. Recruitment specialist
6. Team Leader
7. Department Head
8. Project Manager
9. Supervisor
10. Senior Manager
11. Junior Manager
12. Executive director
13. Consultant
14. Other: _____
15. I prefer not to say

G5Q6. How many years of experience do you have in Human Resources or management?

1. Less than 1 year
2. 1–3 years

3. 4–6 years
4. 7–10 years
5. 11–15 years
6. 15–20 years
7. More than 20 years
8. I prefer not to say

G5Q7. Where do you currently work? [Translate adapting to each national context; keep the population numbers]

1. Big city (more than 1,000,000 of inhabitants)
2. Medium-city (Between 100,000 and 1,000,000 inhabitants)
3. Town (Less than 100,000 inhabitants)
4. City suburbs or outskirts
5. Rural village
6. Farm or home in the countryside
7. I prefer not to say

G5Q8. What sector does your organisation operate in? (If G1Q8= 1,2 or 3)

1. Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing
2. Arts and Entertainment
3. Cleaning
4. Care services
5. Construction and Manufacturing
6. Education and Training
7. Executive and Government Leadership
8. Finance and Insurance services
9. Hair and beauty industry
10. Healthcare and Social Work
11. Technology (ICT)
12. Media and Communications
13. Nonprofit Work in an NGO, policy and advocacy
14. Professional Services (legal, consulting, accounting)
15. Public Administration and Government
16. Shop salesperson (retail)
17. Transportation and Logistics
18. Waiter and tourism services
19. I prefer not to say
20. Other: _____

G5Q8b. Is your main job in the public or the private sector?

Companies with public ownership but private management and working conditions should be considered part of the private sector in this survey.

1. Public sector (administration, public services, state-owned companies)

2. Private (private companies)
3. Third sector (NGOs, associations, foundations, non-profit cooperatives)
4. Prefer not to say
5. Other:

G5Q9. How many employees work at your workplace?

1. Less than 5
2. Between 5 and 20
3. 21-50
4. 51-100
5. 101-500
6. More than 500
7. Non aplicable
8. I prefer not to answer

G5Q10. How would you classify the size of the organization you work for?

1. Local
2. Regional
3. National
4. International
5. I prefer not to say

G6. Experiences

G6Q1. For each of the following types of discrimination, please indicate to what extent you believe this occurs in your workplace. *Even if you haven't seen it directly, we'd still like to hear your impression.*

Subquestions:

1. Skin Colour
2. Ethnic origin
3. Migrant background
4. Nationality
5. Gender
6. Age
7. Gender identity
8. Sexual orientation
9. Religion or belief
10. Disability
11. Social class or economic status
12. Physical appearance
13. Weight or body size
14. Mental health

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionaly	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G6Q2. In the past five years, has your organisation employed someone who was perceived as or openly transgender or non-binary?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I don't know

G6Q3. (If G6Q2=1) Over the past five years, to what extent have you noticed, been informed of, or had reports of the following forms of harassment against transgender and non-binary people in your workplace?

Subquestions:

10. Name calling, such as personal attacks or insults
11. Mobbing
12. Ridiculing (making jokes about them)
13. Other verbal insults/abuse/humiliation
14. Other non-verbal insults, abuse, humiliation (such as texts or images)
15. Excessive/constant negative comments
16. Spreading rumours or lies
17. Aggressive gestures (such as pointing)
18. Isolation from something or somebody

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionaly	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G6Q4. (If G6Q2=1) Over the past five years, to what extent have you seen, been informed of, or had reports of the following forms of violence against transgender and non-binary people in your workplace?

Subquestions

1. Destroying/ stealing personal belongings
2. Striking doors or objects
3. Using physical force to intimidate or control
4. Using a weapon or object to intimidate or harm
5. Grabbing
6. Pushing
7. Hitting
8. Making degrading sexual remarks
9. Someone watched them in an intimate situation without their consent (e.g., in a changing room or toilet)

10. Exposing oneself or making obscene gestures
11. Non-consensual physical contact (e.g., groping or inappropriate touching)
12. They have been followed in public by work-related individuals in an intrusive or intimidating manner
13. Unsolicited sharing of sexually explicit material
14. Unwanted sexual advances
15. Rape

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G6Q5. Over the past five years, has anyone in your organization come out as transgender or non-binary, or has been undergoing a gender affirmation (transition) process?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I don't know

G6Q6 (If G6Q5= 1) During the person's gender affirmation process, to what extent have you noticed, been informed of, or had reports of the following situations?

Subquestions:

1. Rejection or discriminatory attitudes from colleagues or supervisors
2. Inappropriate comments or invasive questions about their transition
3. Changes in how colleagues treat them after coming out
4. Opposition from management or human resources
5. Difficulties in changing their name and gender in the organisation's internal Systems
6. Use of their wrong pronouns
7. Use of their old name
8. Issues or resistance from co-workers regarding restroom or changing room use
9. Changes in how their professional skills are perceived after transitioning
10. Discrimination in promotions or project assignments
11. They have been reassigned to a non-customer-facing role without them requesting for it
12. Loss of their job

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G6Q7 (If G6Q5= yes) To what extent have gender affirmation processes been supported within your organisation, based on your knowledge and experience?

Subquestions:

1. Acceptance and correct use of their name and pronouns
2. Support and understanding from co-workers
3. Organisation support in updating official documentation
4. Access to restrooms and changing rooms that align with their gender identity
5. Changes in dress codes or uniforms to match their gender identity

Answers:

1. Never	2. Occasionally	3. At times	4. Frequently	5. Very frequently	6. Not applicable
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G6Q8. To what extent does your organization ensure the following for trans and non-binary individuals?

Subquestions:

1. The same or not fewer opportunities to be hired
2. The same or not fewer opportunities to be promoted

Answers:

1. Not at all	2. A little	3. Somehow	4. Quite	5. Totally	Not applicable
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G7. Training needs

G7Q1. Do you think it would be necessary to provide training to the human resources team on the following areas related to trans and non-binary people? *If your organisation has already addressed these topics or the staff is well-informed, you can select 'unnecessary' or 'strongly unnecessary'. We want to identify which areas need deeper work.*

Subquestions:

1. Training in Key concepts: meaning of the LGBTIQ+ acronym; differences between sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression; myths and realities about sexual and gender diversity
2. LGBTIQ+-phobia and transphobia: what is it and how it manifests in the workplace
3. Trans and non-binary workplace experiences: personal testimonies
4. Laws related to LGBTI rights and preventing LGBTI discrimination in the workplace
5. Specific labour rights for transgender people
6. Needs and rights of people undergoing gender transition within the organisation
7. Good practices for gender-inclusive hiring and onboarding processes
8. Well-being of transgender people at work
9. How to manage subtle and visible discrimination against transgender people at work
10. Communication skills and advocacy for LGBTIQ+ rights within the Organization

11. Handling resistance to LGBTIQ+ inclusion and fostering constructive dialogue
12. Providing training for leadership and management teams on fostering an inclusive workplace
13. Benefits of having an inclusive workplace for employee well-being and performance
14. Benefits of having an inclusive workplace for business growth and brand reputation

Answers:

1.Strongly unnecessary	2.Unnecessary	3.Neither necessary nor unnecessary	4.Necessary	5. Strongly necessary	6.Unsure / Don't know
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G8. Organizational culture

G8Q1 Does your organisation have any approved equality plan in place?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I don't know

G8Q2 (If G8Q1=1). Does your plan include specific protective measures for individuals with sexual, affective, and gender diversity?

1. Yes
2. No
3. I don't know

G8Q3 (if G8Q2= 1). Are the following measures included in your organization's equality plan or under development?

Subquestions:

1. LGBTIQ+ diversity training for all staff membres
2. Non-discrimination policies specifically for LGBTI and transgender individuals
3. LGBTIQ+ harassment prevention protocol
4. Protocol to support transgender and non-binary individuals
5. Protocol for supporting employees during gender transition in the workplace
6. Measures to ensure access to bathrooms and changing rooms according to gender identity
7. Measures to ensure the corporate use of the employee chosen name
8. Measures to promote LGBTIQ+ visibility and inclusion in corporate culture

Answers:

1. Yes	2.No	3.I don't know
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G8Q4 Do you think that the plans, protocols, and measures your organization has in place regarding gender and sexual diversity are applicable in practice?

1. Yes
2. No
3. Not sure

G8Q5 Have these plans, protocols, or measures been applied in any situation?

1. Never
2. Occasionally
3. At times
4. Frequently
5. Very frequently
6. Don't know

G8Q6 How would you assess the way these plans, protocols, or measures have been implemented?

1. Not effective at all
2. Not very effective
3. Neutral
4. Somewhat effective
5. Very effective
6. I don't know

G8Q7 Do you believe the following situations take place in your organisation?

Subquestions:

1. Jokes or remarks targeting the LGB community are common in the workplace
2. Jokes or remarks targeting the trans or non-binary community are common in the workplace
3. Employees are presumed to be heterosexual unless stated otherwise
4. LGB individuals are asked personal questions as naturally as non-LGB individuals are
5. Transgender individuals are asked personal questions as naturally as cisgender individuals are
6. ("Cisgender" refers to people that are not trans)
7. There is equal recognition and visibility of LGBTIQ+ relationships as heterosexual relationships (e.g., mentioning partners, displaying family photos)
8. Inclusive language is consistently used in workplace communication (e.g., avoiding gendered assumptions, using correct pronouns)

9. There are subtle or indirect forms of exclusion towards transgender employees (e.g., being left out of conversations, networking opportunities)
10. Leadership positions within the organisation include people who are openly trans or non-binary

Answers:

1. Not at all	2. A little	3. Somehow	4. Quite	5. Totally	6. I don't know
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G9Q1. (If TQ= 1+2 or 1+3) Would you like to also answer the questions addressed to trans, non-binary, and LGBTIQ+ individuals?

1. Yes, I would like to continue
2. No, I prefer to end the survey here

END

Thank you for your time. The results of the survey will be published at the end of the research phase. If you know anyone who might be interested in participating, please feel free to share the link. We especially encourage trans and non-binary individuals to take part in the survey. If you would like to share your experience in an interview, or if you would like to receive updates on the implementation of the Transcending Barriers project, you can contact the research team of the country you live in, at: [add partner's email]

Appendix 1: Informed consent form for transgender and non-binary participants

This document provides all the necessary information you need to freely decide whether you want to participate in this study. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

THE PROJECT

Project title: *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace*

Participating organizations

Università degli Studi di Brescia (Italy), Coordinator; Universitat de Girona (Spain); Glas Foundation Bulgaria (Bulgaria); Fondazione Human Age Institute (Italy); ALDA, Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale (France); Associazione Ambasciata della Democrazia Locale a Zavidovici – Onlus Impresa Sociale (Italy); Vytauto Didziojo Universitetas (Lithuania); Asociacija Lietuvos Geju Lyga (Lithuania); UnitelmaSapienza (Italy)

Contact/Principal Investigator

The principal investigator of the project is [name of the national team leader], who can be reached at [institutional email address].

Target group of this interview

Transgender and non-binary people

Description and objectives

The Transcending Barriers project aims to promote trans inclusion in the workplace by enhancing the skills of human resources professionals, raising awareness and supporting trans individuals through mentoring programmes.

The project's general objectives are:

- To strengthen the ability of HR professionals and managers to engage in diversity management practices, specifically regarding trans individuals
- To prepare and develop a training curriculum to tackle the training needs of HR professionals and managers
- To improve access to the workplace through mentoring activities that target trans individuals
- To enhance knowledge about, and the application of, trans rights in the workplace through awareness-raising activities in participating countries

The project's target groups are: HR professionals and managers, transgender and non-binary individuals and policymakers. The indirect beneficiaries are the LGBTIQ+ community.

ABOUT THE INTERVIEW

Objective of the interview

For transgender or non-binary individuals, the main objective of the interviews is to explore the experiences and needs of transgender and non-binary people related to work and work access. These, along with the needs identified from human resources professionals, will inform the training curriculum and mentoring programme.

Interview characteristics

The interviews are semi-structured and open. The average duration will be between 50 and 60 minutes and the audio will be recorded, unless otherwise specified. During this interview, we will collect the sociodemographic data that you share with us. We will ask you about your age, country of birth, legal status, gender, sexual orientation, employment, education, religion, living conditions, disabilities, your place of residence (city/town/rural) and your work sector. You can choose not to answer any of the questions.

Confidentiality and data protection

If the transcripts are transcribed or used to prepare reports, names or other information that could identify the interviewee will not be used, thus ensuring anonymity.

The research team will securely store all collected data and files at [name of the organization or university], which complies with data protection regulations. The data will never be used for any purpose other than that specified below. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for collecting, processing and securely storing the anonymous data. You can contact them by email at [institutional email address].

In compliance with current legislation on personal data protection, data confidentiality and protection are guaranteed in accordance with European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

If you have any questions about data storage or wish to exercise your right to revoke permission to store your data, you can do so by contacting the [name of the organization] Data Protection Officer at [institutional email address]. The data will be automatically deleted after 5 years.

What will we do with the results of the interview?

Once the research is complete, we will write a final report that will publish the results in academic journals and/or other publications. We will also hold various events to present the results. This will help to raise awareness amongst those involved in personnel selection processes or positions of responsibility – including politicians – about the rights of trans people and thus improve their inclusion and promotion in the workplace. Although we may include content from this interview, it will always be anonymous.

We will also create a training curriculum and mentoring programme.

Risks and drawbacks

During the interview, you may be asked to recall difficult situations you experienced, which could have emotional consequences. To avoid reliving the episode in a traumatic way to the extent possible (which could lead to secondary victimization), you will be allowed at all times to stop answering a question or even leave the interview. If you feel unwell, the interviewer will make every reasonable effort to ensure and promote your well-being. Choosing a suitable location for the interview to guarantee privacy for the conversation has been prioritized. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for addressing any discomfort or distress that may result from your participation in this study. If you experience any such effects and require additional support, you can contact [national contact information] for assistance.

Benefits

Currently, there is very little data available on the employment situation of transgender and non-binary people in [add name of the country]. Your participation will help us to better understand this reality and design useful materials tailored to each context and its real needs. Even though this study will not directly benefit the participants, it will benefit the transgender community, professionals working in human resources and the general public. The project will provide new insights into transgender issues, discrimination and survivor support using an intersectional approach, providing innovative tools and materials for professionals and survivors, as well as advice and proposals for policymakers. The project will benefit the general public by increasing knowledge about the personal and social consequences of bias-motivated violence and discrimination. By training professionals, we also hope to create a long-term positive transformation throughout society.

Research participation and the right to withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary. You are not required to participate if you do not wish to. If you decide to participate, you may withdraw from the study at any time without any explanation and without negative consequences. We only request that you inform us through

one of the available communication channels. At the discretion of the research team, you may be withdrawn from the study for either of the following reasons: a) failure to meet the requirements established in the study; or b) discontinuation of the study for any reason.

Your withdrawal from the study will not affect the legality of the data processing. If you withdraw, your personal data will not be stored.

Right to additional information about the study

You will have the opportunity to ask any questions about the study during the research process. The research contact person will be available to address your concerns or questions about the study. You will also be informed of any new findings during the study that may affect your participation in future research. If, during or after the study, you wish to discuss your rights as a participant, your participation or your concerns regarding the process. If you feel pressured to participate or continue in this or in future studies, you may contact the authorities, who can help you discuss these issues (or, if necessary, you can ask for a representative, such as a university ethics committee). You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

SIGNATURE

The interviewee

I have read the information about the research project and have had the opportunity to ask questions about my concerns, which have been answered. I understand that the anonymous information (without personal identifiers) gathered in this project may be made available to other researchers after the project ends.

I, [first and surname(s)], agree to participate in this research project voluntarily.
I have received a copy of this consent form.

Signature:

.....

Date:

The interviewer

I, [first and surname(s)], declare that the objectives and procedures used in this research project have been explained. I have also discussed the risks and potential drawbacks that may arise and have answered all questions related to the study to the best of my knowledge.

Signature:

.....

Date:

This document will be signed in duplicate, leaving one copy for the interviewee and one for the organization/interviewer.

Appendix 2: Consent form for human resources and management professionals

This document provides all the necessary information you need to freely decide whether you want to participate in this study. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

THE PROJECT

Project title: *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace*

Participating organizations

Università degli Studi di Brescia (Italy), Coordinator; Universitat de Girona (Spain); Glas Foundation Bulgaria (Bulgaria); Fondazione Human Age Institute (Italy); ALDA, Associazione Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale (France); Associazione Ambasciata della Democrazia Locale a Zavidovici – Onlus Impresa Sociale (Italy); Vytauto Didziojo Universitetas (Lithuania); Asociacija Lietuvos Geju Lyga (Lithuania); UnitelmaSapienza (Italy).

Contact/Principal Investigator

The principal investigator of the project is [name of the national team leader], who can be reached at [institutional email address].

Target group of this interview

Human resources and management professionals

Description and objectives

The Transcending Barriers project aims to promote trans inclusion in the workplace by enhancing the skills of human resources professionals, raising awareness and supporting trans individuals through mentoring programmes.

The project's general objectives are:

- To strengthen the ability of HR professionals and managers to engage in diversity management practices, specifically regarding trans individuals
- To prepare and develop a training curriculum to tackle the training needs of HR professionals and managers
- To improve access to the workplace through mentoring activities that target trans individuals
- To enhance knowledge about, and the application of, trans rights in the workplace through awareness-raising activities in participating countries

The project's target groups are: HR professionals and managers, transgender and non-binary individuals and policymakers. The indirect beneficiaries are the LGBTIQ+ community.

ABOUT THE INTERVIEW

Objective of the interview

The main objective of the interviews is to explore the perceptions and needs of human resources professionals related to diversity management, specifically regarding trans individuals. The information gathered, along with the experiences and needs identified from transgender and non-binary individuals, will inform the training curriculum and mentoring programme.

Interview characteristics

The interviews are semi-structured and open. The average duration will be between 50 and 60 minutes and the audio will be recorded, unless otherwise specified. During this interview, we will collect the sociodemographic data that you share with us. We will ask you about your age, country of birth, legal status, gender, sexual orientation, employment, education, religion, living conditions, disabilities, your place of residence (city/town/rural) and your work sector. You can choose not to answer any of the questions.

Confidentiality and data protection

If the transcripts are transcribed or used to prepare reports, names or other information that could identify the interviewee will not be used, thus ensuring anonymity.

The research team will securely store all collected data and files in the [name of organization or university] repositories, complying with data protection regulations. The data will never be used for any purpose other than that specified below. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for collecting, processing and securely storing the anonymous data. You can contact them by email at [institutional email address].

In compliance with current legislation on personal data protection, data confidentiality and protection are guaranteed in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

If you have any questions about data storage or wish to exercise your right to revoke permission to store your data, you can do so by contacting the [name of the organization] Data Protection Officer at [institutional email address]. The data will be automatically deleted after 5 years.

What will we do with the results of the interview?

Once the research is complete, we will write a final report that will publish the results in academic journals and/or other publications. We will also hold various events to present the results. This will help to raise awareness amongst those involved in personnel selection processes or positions of responsibility – including politicians – about the rights of trans people and thus improve their inclusion and promotion in the workplace. Although we may include content from this interview, it will always be anonymous.

We will also create a training curriculum and a mentoring programme.

Risks and drawbacks

During the interview, you may be asked to recall difficult situations you experienced, which could have emotional consequences. To avoid reliving the episode in a traumatic way to the extent possible (which could lead to secondary victimization), you will be allowed at all times to stop answering a question or even leave the interview. If you feel unwell, the interviewer will make any effort to ensure and promote your well-being. Choosing a suitable location for the interview to guarantee privacy for the conversation has been prioritized. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for addressing any discomfort or distress that may result from your participation in this study. If you experience any such effects and need additional support, you can contact [national contact information] for assistance.

Benefits

Currently, there is very little data available on the employment situation of transgender and non-binary people in [add name of the country]. Your participation will help us to better understand this reality and design useful materials tailored to each context and its real needs.

Even though this study will not directly benefit the participants, it will benefit the transgender community, professionals working in human resources and the general public. The project will provide new insights into transgender issues, discrimination and survivor support using an intersectional approach, providing innovative tools and materials for professionals and survivors, as well as advice and proposals for policymakers. The project will benefit the general public by increasing knowledge about the personal and social consequences of bias-motivated violence and discrimination. By training professionals, we also hope to create a long-term positive transformation throughout society.

Research participation and the right to withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary. You are not required to participate if you do not wish to. If you decide to participate, you may withdraw from the study at any time without any explanation and without negative consequences. We only request that you inform us through one of the available communication channels. At the discretion of the research team, you may

be withdrawn from the study for either of the following reasons: a) failure to meet the requirements established in the study; or b) discontinuation of the study for any reason.

Your withdrawal from the study will not affect the legality of the data processing. If you withdraw, your personal data will not be stored.

Right to additional information about the study

You will have the opportunity to ask any questions about the study during the research process. The research contact person will be available to address your concerns or questions about the study. You will also be informed of any new findings during the study that may affect your participation in future research. If, during or after the study, you wish to discuss your rights as a participant, your participation or your concerns regarding the process. If you feel pressured to participate or continue in this or in future studies, you may contact the authorities, who can help you discuss these issues (or, if necessary, you can ask for a representative, such as a university ethics committee). You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

SIGNATURE

The interviewee

I have read the information about the research project and have had the opportunity to ask questions about my concerns, which have been answered. I understand that the anonymous information (without personal identifiers) gathered in this project may be made available to other researchers after the project ends.

I, [first and surname(s)], agree to participate in this research project voluntarily.

- The legal representative of the institution/organization where I work was informed about the study objectives and my participation in the interview.

I have received a copy of this consent form.

Signature:

.....

Date:

The interviewer

I, [first and surname(s)], declare that the objectives and procedures used in this research project have been explained. I have also discussed the risks and potential drawbacks that may arise and have answered all questions related to the study to the best of my knowledge.

Signature:

.....

Date:

This document will be signed in duplicate, leaving one copy for the interviewee and one for the organization/interviewer.

Appendix 3: Consent form for organizations

This document provides all the necessary information you need to freely decide whether you want to participate in this study. Please read the following information carefully and ask any questions you may have.

THE PROJECT

Project title: *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace*

Participating organizations

Università degli Studi di Brescia (Italy), Coordinator; Universitat de Girona (Spain); Glas Foundation Bulgaria (Bulgaria); Fondazione Human Age Institute (Italy); ALDA, Associazione Européenne pour la Democratie Locale (France); Associazione Ambasciata della Democrazia Locale a Zavidovici – Onlus Impresa Sociale (Italy); Vytauto Didziojo Universitetas (Lithuania); Asociacija Lietuvos Geju Lyga (Lithuania); UnitelmaSapienza (Italy)

Contact/ Principal Investigator

The principal investigator of the project is [name of the national team leader], who can be reached at [institutional email address].

Target group of this consent form

Legal representative of the institution/organization where the head of human resources (interviewee) works.

Description and objectives

The *Transcending Barriers* project aims to promote trans inclusion in the workplace by enhancing Human Resources professionals' skills, raising awareness, and supporting trans individuals through mentoring programs.

The project's general objectives are:

- To strengthen the ability of HR professionals and managers to engage in diversity management practices, specifically regarding trans individuals.
- To prepare and develop a training curriculum to tackle the training needs of HR professionals and managers.
- To improve access to the workplace through mentoring activities that target trans individuals.
- To enhance knowledge about, and the application of, trans rights in the workplace through awareness-raising activities in participating countries.

The project's target groups are: HR professionals and managers, transgender and non-binary individuals and policymakers. The indirect beneficiaries are the LGBTIQ+ community.

ABOUT THE INTERVIEW

Objective of the interview

The main objective of the interviews is to explore the perceptions and needs of human resources professionals related to diversity management, specifically regarding trans individuals. The information gathered, along with the experiences and needs identified from transgender and non-binary individuals, will inform the training curriculum and mentoring programme.

Interview characteristics

The interviews are semi-structured and open. The average duration will be between 50 and 60 minutes and the audio will be recorded, unless otherwise specified. During this interview, we will collect the sociodemographic data that you share with us. We will ask you about your age, country of birth, legal status, gender, sexual orientation, employment, education, religion, living conditions, disabilities, your place of residence (city/town/rural) and your work sector. You can choose not to answer any of the questions.

Confidentiality and data protection

If the transcripts are transcribed or used to prepare reports, names or other information that could identify the interviewee will not be used, thus ensuring anonymity.

The research team will securely store all collected data and files in the University of Girona's repositories, complying with data protection regulations. The data will never be used for any purpose other than that specified below. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for collecting, processing and securely storing the anonymous data. You can contact them by email at [institutional email address].

In compliance with current legislation on personal data protection, data confidentiality and protection are guaranteed in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

If you have any questions about data storage or wish to exercise your right to revoke permission to store your data, you can do so by contacting the [name of the organization] Data Protection Officer at [institutional email address]. The data will be automatically deleted after 5 years.

What will we do with the results of the interview?

Once the research is complete, we will write a final report that will publish the results in academic journals and/or other publications. We will also hold various events to present the results. This will help to raise awareness amongst those involved in personnel selection processes or positions of responsibility – including politicians – about the rights of trans

people and thus improve their inclusion and promotion in the workplace. Although we may include content from this interview, it will always be anonymous.

We will also create a training curriculum and a mentoring programme.

Risks and drawbacks

During the interview, you may be asked to recall difficult situations you experienced, which could have emotional consequences. To avoid reliving the episode in a traumatic way to the extent possible (which could lead to secondary victimization), you will be allowed at all times to stop answering a question or even leave the interview. If you feel unwell, the interviewer will make any effort to ensure and promote your well-being. Choosing a suitable location for the interview to guarantee privacy for the conversation has been prioritized. [Name of the organization or university] is responsible for addressing any discomfort or distress that may result from your participation in this study. If you experience any such effects and need additional support, you can contact [national contact information] for assistance.

Benefits

Currently, there is very little data available on the employment situation of transgender and non-binary people in [add name of the country]. Your participation will help us to better understand this reality and design useful materials tailored to each context and its real needs.

Even though this study will not directly benefit the participants, it will benefit the transgender community, professionals working in human resources and the general public. The project will provide new insights into transgender issues, discrimination and survivor support using an intersectional approach, providing innovative tools and materials for professionals and survivors, as well as advice and proposals for policymakers. The project will benefit the general public by increasing knowledge about the personal and social consequences of bias-motivated violence and discrimination. By training professionals, we also hope to create a long-term positive transformation throughout society.

Research participation and the right to withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary. You are not required to participate if you do not wish to. If you decide to participate, you may withdraw from the study at any time without any explanation and without negative consequences. We only request that you inform us through one of the available communication channels. At the discretion of the research team, you may be withdrawn from the study for either of the following reasons: a) failure to meet the requirements established in the study; or b) discontinuation of the study for any reason.

Your withdrawal from the study will not affect the legality of the data processing. If you withdraw, your personal data will not be stored.

Right to additional information about the study

You will have the opportunity to ask any questions about the study during the research process. The research contact person will be available to address your concerns or questions about the study. You will also be informed of any new findings during the study that may affect your participation in future research. If, during or after the study, you wish to discuss your rights as a participant, your participation or your concerns regarding the process. If you feel pressured to participate or continue in this or in future studies, you may contact the authorities, who can help you discuss these issues (or, if necessary, you can ask for a representative, such as a university ethics committee). You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.

SIGNATURE

The legal representative

I, [first and surname(s)]
....., have read the information about the research project and have had the opportunity to ask questions about my concerns, which have been answered.

I understand that the anonymous information (without personal identifiers) gathered in this project may be made available to other researchers at any time after the project ends.

I give permission to my employee, [first and surname(s) of the employee], to participate voluntarily in the research project.

I have received a copy of this consent form.

Signature:

.....

Date:

The interviewer

I, [first and surname(s)]
....., declare that the objectives and procedures used in this research project have been explained. I have also discussed the risks and potential drawbacks that may arise and have answered all questions related to the study to the best of my knowledge.

Signature:

.....

Date:

This document will be signed in duplicate, leaving one copy for the interviewee and one for the organization/interviewer.

Appendix 4: Confidentiality agreement

..... (full name), with ID (foreigner identification number, passport), acting on my own behalf,

DECLARE:

First: That I am part of the research project *Transcending Barriers: Promoting Trans Inclusion in the Workplace* at [name of the organization].

Second: That the information on data protection at [name of the organization] can be consulted at [link to the information].

Third: That if I provide data for the project, I have the right to do so.

I COMMIT:

First: To process the personal data to which I have access in accordance with applicable legislation and the regulations of [name of the organization].

Second: Not to use the data for purposes other than relating to the abovementioned project.

Third: To observe professional secrecy regarding the data being processed, to maintain absolute confidentiality and discretion over any data I may become aware of during the project, and not to share the data provided with any third party, not even for storage. This limitation does not apply to information that is or becomes public domain or was already in my possession.

Fourth: To implement the necessary technical and organizational measures to ensure the security of the data I access, in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the instructions provided by [name of the organization] in order to prevent their alteration, loss or unauthorized processing.

Fifth: If I have access to previously pseudonymized data, not to attempt to identify the individuals to whom the data refers by any means, whether direct or indirect, and to ensure that re-identification cannot occur in case of publication.

Sixth: Once the research project is completed, to destroy the personal data or return it to the principal investigator, as instructed.

Seventh: To be held liable by [name of the organization] for any damages caused due to non-compliance with any of these commitments, including any arising from third-party claims or from sanctioning proceedings initiated by courts or data protection authorities.

Eighth: To comply with these confidentiality commitments even after the end of my contractual or collaborative relationship with [name of the organization].

Signed in [city] on[day/month/year]

Signature